
THE PLACES OF WORSHIP (SPECIAL PROVISIONS) ACT, 1991

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ABSTRACT

Throughout the world, religious sites serve as places of worship, cultural heritage, and symbols of identity. The sacred places have, however, often been the subject of conflicts or neglect over time. In order to protect places of worship and promote religious freedom, the "Places of Worship Act 1991" was enacted. An outline of the historical context, key provisions, and implications of the Act is presented in this research paper, with particular attention paid to its impact on the preservation and management of religious sites. Legislators passed the act in response to urgent concerns surrounding places of worship. These places of worship were defined², protected, and regulated under this framework. In this study, the purpose is to put light on the importance of the act as it relates to facilitating cultural conservation by analyzing its background and provisions. Tensions over places of worship have caused conflicts and social divisions. Therefore, it is important to understand the history of the act that led to its enactment to understand the objectives and purpose of the act. The Challenges and tensions in the past led to the enactment of the Places of Worship Act, 1991. The research paper will draw attention to the case studies to get a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of the act.

I. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION:

The partition of India led to the creation of two separate nations, India and Pakistan, with a significant population exchange and large-scale communal violence along religious lines. This resulted in the displacement and migration of millions of people, including the minority communities in both countries.

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² The Places of Worship Act, 1991, Section 2, No.42, Acts of Parliament, 1991(India).

The Babri Masjid-Ram Janmabhoomi³ dispute is a long-standing and highly contentious issue in India. The Babri Masjid, a mosque in Ayodhya, Uttar Pradesh, was claimed by some Hindus to be the birthplace of Lord Rama.

An opinion was made "Steps for Maintaining Status Quo of Religious Shrines and Places of Worship"⁴ as they were on August 15, 1947, before the "Places of Worship Act" being brought before the legislature, was introduced in the Lok Sabha by MP Zainal Abedin on July 12, 1991.

The act declares that the religious character of any place of worship existing as of August 15, 1947, shall continue to be the same, and no person shall convert it into a different religious place of worship.

The resolution made by Abedin was taken away by himself on 10th September, the day when Union Minister S.B. Chavan brought a bill in Lok Sabha and got the majority approval. It was approved by Rajya Sabha on 12th September and signed into law on 18th September by R. Venkatraman the President.

"The Places of Worship (Special Provisions) Act" was enacted in 1991, during the peak of the Ram Janmabhoomi movement. The Act was passed by Parliament and received the approval of the President. It is noteworthy that the Act was ratified by P V Narasimha Rao, a Congress representative, at a time when the Babri Masjid was still standing.⁵

Because 15th August 1947 symbolize the end of colonial rule in India and provides a constitutional framework for resolving historical issues, the legislature decided to freeze characteristics of religious places on this day.

II. FEATURES OF THE PLACES OF WORSHIP ACT

- Under section 3 of the Act transforming a house of worship of one denomination into a house of worship of another or even a place of some section of that religious group is restricted.
- The spiritual status of that holy place should same as it was on the 15th of August 1947, stated under section 4(1).

³ M.Siddiq (D) Thr. Lrs. vs Mahant Suresh Das 2019 SCC SC 1440.

⁴ The Places of Worship Act,1991, Section 4, No.42, Acts of Parliament,1991(India).

⁵ Shreshth Srivastava & Vaishali Gaurha, The Controversy surrounding The Places of Worship Act 1991, Volume-IV (2021), SLR, 269, 271-272.

- A lawsuit regarding the conversion of a “place of worship” that was on August 15, 1947 is prohibited under Section 4(2) that is one lawsuit is already pending before the court.
- As Stated in Section 6 of the Act, which defines the penalties for such a breach, a person who violates the conditions of the Act may be sentenced to up to three years in jail and a sizable fine.

III. PROVISIONS OF THE ACT

Section 1

This Section stated that the Act is applicable throughout India and on the 11th of July 1991, it became effective.

Section 2

In this Section expressions like “place of worship”, “conversion”, and “commencement of this act” are defined. The term "Place of Worship" refers to any building used for people’s religious worshipping, including a “temple”, “mosque”, “gurudwara”, “church”, “monastery”, or “congregation”.

Section 3

According to Section 3 of the “Places of Worship Act”, no one is allowed to alter places of worship, utilize them for the worship of members of another religious organization or section, or allow their own members to worship there.⁶

Section 4

As stated in Section 4, the religious nature of Places of worship as it was on 15th August 1947 is formally decided to remain unaltered from that day.

Regardless of whether or not such a suit, appeal, or other proceedings regarding the transformation of the religious identity of any house of worship was pending when this Act went into effect, none of such actions may be taken thereafter in any court, tribunal, or other authority.⁷

Section 5

⁶ M.Siddiq (D) Thr. Lrs. vs Mahant Suresh Das 2019 SCC SC 1440.

⁷ Committee of Management, Anjuman Intezamia Masjid, Varanasi v. Smt. Rakhi Singh and Others 2023 ALL 377.

Any legal action, appeal, or other activity regarding the place of worship often referred to as Ram Janam Bhumi-Babri Masjid in Ayodhya in the State of Uttar Pradesh is exempt from the Act.⁸

Section 6

The Act includes provisions that stipulate a penalty of up to three years of imprisonment and a fine for non-compliance with its requirements. It is important to note that irrespective of the provisions outlined in Section 116 of the Indian Penal Code, individuals who engage in a criminal conspiracy to commit an offense or aid and abet its commission are subject to legal consequences and liable for punishment.

Section 7

The Act establishes that if there is a disagreement between the provisions of the Places of Worship Act and any other laws currently in effect, the provisions of the Places of Worship Act will prevail and take precedence over the conflicting laws.⁹

Section 8

A person guilty of an offence punishable by Section 6 of this Act shall be barred, according to "Section 8(1)(j) of the Representation of People Act, 1951."

IV. THE RELEVANCE OF PLACES OF WORSHIP ACT IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

• United Kingdom

In order to register Places of Worship, the United Kingdom passed the Places for Worship Registration Act of 1855. The Act aims to uphold the rights of religious minorities and support their ability to practise their religion freely¹⁰. The use and protection of religious structures were further addressed by later legislation, such as the "Places of Worship (Enfranchisement) Act 1920" and the "Places of Worship (Use Classes) Order 2020".

• Malaysia

The "Places of Worship (Special Provisions) Act 1965" exists in Malaysia, and it protects places of worship from being destroyed or moved without first consulting the appropriate religious

⁸ M.Siddiq (D) Thr. Lrs. vs Mahant Suresh Das 2019 SCC SC 1440.

⁹ Smt. Shakeela Khatoon Vs. Jangle Wali Masjid Waqf No. 277 And Another 2017 SCC Online All 3466.

¹⁰ Gov.UK, www.gov.uk (28th June,2023).

authorities. The Act's goal is to ensure the peaceful coexistence of various religious communities by protecting these places of worship and resolving any disputes involving religious properties.¹¹

- **South Africa**

The "National Heritage Resources Act 1999" in South Africa contains measures for the management and protection of places of worship as a component of the nation's cultural heritage. The Act creates a framework for locating, protecting, and promoting religious sites and promotes local involvement in their preservation.

- **Singapore**

The "Preservation of Monuments Act" in Singapore offers legal protection for places of worship as well as other buildings with national, historical, architectural, or cultural significance. To protect designated religious structures for future generations, the Act regulates their modification, relocation, and demolition.

- **India**

In India, the "Places of Worship (Special Provisions) Act 1991" was introduced to maintain the status quo of religious places as it existed on August 15, 1947, the day of India's independence. The Act seeks to protect the religious character of places of worship and prevent their conversion or destruction.

It prohibits the filing of lawsuits seeking the alteration of religious places and aims to maintain communal harmony by preserving the religious sentiments associated with these sites.¹²

V. CRITICISM OF THE ACT

The Places of Worship Act has gained both support and criticism in India since its enactment. While some view it as a necessary measure to maintain communal harmony and protect the religious character of places of worship, others have raised various criticisms.

- The Act has been criticised for effectively freezing legal claims and issues pertaining to places of worship as of August 15, 1947. Critics claim that this clause prevents people and groups from using the judicial system to address grievances or historical wrongs involving religious properties.

¹¹ malaysiakini, www.malaysiakini.com, (28th June,2023).

¹² Sanjana Santosh, The Places of Worship Act, iPleaders, (27th June, 2023), <https://blog.ipleaders.in/place-of-worship-act-1991>.

- The Act, according to critics, violates the secularism concept contained in the Indian Constitution. They contend that the Act contradicts the state's commitment to treating all religions equally by indirectly favouring one religious group over another by freezing the status quo of holy places.
- Critics claim that the Act makes it more difficult to pursue justice and peace in situations where religious sites have been disputed or converted. Some contend that by outlawing legal claims that seek to change the status quo, it maintains old grievances and undermines efforts to settle disputes peacefully.
- The Act has also faced criticism for its ambiguous language and scope. Critics argue that the lack of clear definitions and guidelines regarding what constitutes a religious place of worship and the limitations of the Act's application have led to confusion and inconsistent interpretations, potentially resulting in further disputes.

VI. WAY FORWARD

India was not a constitutional democracy before August 15, 1947. When a temple was allegedly destroyed in the Middle centuries, there was no established legal system. The rule of law was absent at one point, and the polity had an expansionist outlook.

The medieval polity and the modern Indian state differed significantly from one another. However, the rule of law and constitutional ideals are now present in our contemporary democracy. Recent occurrences seem to be a part of a bigger plan to create division among the country's many communities to tear its social and political structure into parts.

In the related case, the Supreme Court determined that it was unlawful to destroy the Babri Masjid. The Court concluded that as essential elements of the constitution, "the State has a constitutional commitment and constitutional duty to uphold the equality of all religions and secularism."

This Act is necessary to preserve the secular features of India, according to the Court's interpretation of the Indian Constitution. Government, executive branch, and judicial decisions must not be taken in political influence or in sentiments, they must be based on laws and constitutional Principles.

VII. LANDMARK JUDGEMENT

A. Gyanvapi Mosque Case¹³

“The Gyanvapi mosque” and the “Kashi Vishwanath temple complex” in Varanasi have been at the center of a contentious dispute, prompting significant attention and controversy. The dispute emerged when five Hindu women petitioned for the right to worship idols within the Gyanvapi Mosque premises, claiming that the masjid was constructed after the destruction of a Hindu Mandir in the 17th century. In response, a Varanasi court recently issued an order for the comprehensive video recording of the Gyanvapi Masjid complex to investigate the veracity of this claim. However, the mosque board and the Uttar Pradesh Sunni Central Waqf Board opposed this order. To facilitate the petitioners' appeal to the Supreme Court, the Allahabad High Court, in a decision on April 21, abstained from involvement in the survey. The Muslim side involved in the dispute has invoked Section 4 of the “Places of Worship (Special Provisions) Act, 1991”, which prohibits the initiation of legal action or procedures to alter the holy feature of any place of worship as it was on 15th of August 1947. They argue that the act safeguards the status quo and prevents any changes to religious sites that existed at the time of India's independence.

There are currently two petitions before the Supreme Court that question the Act's validity. On behalf of Sanatan Vedic practitioners, the “Vishwa Bhadra Pujari Purohit Mahasangh trust in Lucknow” filed a petition, and advocate Ashwini Upadhyay filed another.

In his petition, Upadhyay argued that the government did not possess the jurisdiction to enact a law that restricted the right to initiate legal action for the restoration of the sacred site. According to him, this authority was absent. The assertion made is that due to the Act's imposition of limitations on addressing unlawful encroachments on places of worship and pilgrimage, individuals belonging to the Hindu, Jain, Buddhist, and Sikh communities can now institute legal proceedings or approach the High Court.¹⁴

On the other hand, a petition submitted by the “Vishwa Bhadra Pujari Purohit Mahasangh” contested Section 4 of the “Places of Worship (Special Provisions) Act, 1991”. It read, "The challenged Act has restricted the right and remedy against invasion made on sacred property of

¹³ Committee of Management, Anjuman Intezamia Masjid, Varanasi v. Smt. Rakhi Singh and Others 2023 ALL 377.

¹⁴ India Const. art. 226.

Hindus exercising might of power by followers of another faith." The law addresses itself to the State in the same way as it addresses every citizen, it stated. Any person in charge of the nation is obligated to uphold its norms.

These regulations give effect to the Fundamental Duties¹⁵ outlined and are therefore applicable to all citizens. The state is carrying out its legal duty to safeguard the separation of religion and state and the secular character of the state, which are essential to it, by passing this legislation.

B. Ayodhya Case¹⁶

The Supreme Court's Constitution Bench reached a verdict on November 9, 2019, in the case of "M. Siddiq v. Mahant Suresh Das", popularly known as the "Ram Janmabhoomi temple case". This significant ruling provided a complete endorsement for the validity and applicability of the "Places of Worship (Special Provisions) Act, 1991".

According to the Preface of the Act, its purpose is to forbid the transformation of any house of worship and ensure the preservation of the holy feature of such places as it existed on August 15, 1947. Additionally, the Act addresses related matters and incidental issues. Notably, in consensus with Section 5 of the Act, the Ram Janmabhumi-Babri Masjid in Ayodhya is specifically exempted from its provisions.

After reviewing the Act, the Supreme Court declared, "The act established two firm and mandatory norms:

- Section 3 of the Act explicitly stipulates that a place of worship associated with one religious group cannot be transformed into a place of worship affiliated with another denomination, regardless of whether the new group is an offshoot of the original group or represents an entirely different faith. The term "place of worship" in this context encompasses mosques, churches, temples, and other religious structures of all religions and denominations.
- The law ensures the legal protection of the position of every spiritual institution as they were on August 15, 1947. The Court has said that this Act serves to safeguard and uphold the fundamental values enshrined in the Constitution.

During the Ram Janmabhoomi-Babri Masjid claim action, the Supreme Court bench focused on the specific case and did not address the constitutionality of the 1991 Act or review its

¹⁵ India Const. art. 51A.

¹⁶ M.Siddiq (D) Thr. Lrs. vs Mahant Suresh Das 2019 SCC SC 1440.

provisions. While the Allahabad High Court issued decisions that contradicted each other, the Supreme Court made it clear that it upheld the Act. In its 2019 Ayodhya judgment, the Constitution Bench referenced the Act, emphasizing that it promotes the secular values enshrined in the Indian Constitution and prevents any regression from those values. Consequently, the law was enacted to safeguard the fundamental principle of the secular nature of governance outlined in the Indian Constitution.

ANALYSIS:

Background

The Babri Masjid-Ram Janmabhoomi controversy in Ayodhya was one of several communal tensions and disagreements that resulted from religious sites that led to the adoption of the Act. It was designed to remove worries about maintaining the religious nature of places of worship as they were on August 15, 1947.

Objective

The Act's main goal is to preserve the religious character of some places of worship as it was in 1947, forbidding any changes or conversions nature of worship.

Freeze of Status Quo¹⁷

The Act declares that the religious character of any place of worship existing on August 15, 1947, shall continue to be the same as it was at that time. This freeze prevents the conversion of religious places and ensures their preservation.¹⁸

Protection of Places of Worship

The Act protects places of worship by forbidding their conversion, destruction, or modification. By safeguarding the current status of holy sites, it seeks to ensure religious harmony and societal peace.

Exceptions and Disputes

¹⁷ Places of Worship Act, 1991, Section 4, No.42, Acts of Parliament, 1991 (India).

¹⁸ Amish Devgan vs Union of India 2021 SCC Online Del 3353.

The Act acknowledges that there may be disagreements over the religious nature of houses of worship. It allows for the settlement of such issues by court actions brought on by the parties involved.

Criticism

For a number of reasons, the Act has drawn criticism. Some contend that preserving the status of religious places could contribute to the perpetuation of past injustices and impede social advancement. Additionally, some claim that the Act's emphasis on maintaining the status quo may hinder initiatives for racial and ethnic harmony and reconciliation.

Limitations

It is significant to remember that the Act only applies to religious facilities that were present on August 15, 1947. The Act does not apply to houses of worship built after that date. In addition, except from those locations specifically named in the law, the Act does not address conflicts involving other religious locations.

Impact and Significance

The Places of Worship Act, of 1991 plays a crucial role in maintaining religious harmony and protecting the secular character of India. It seeks to prevent conflicts over religious places and ensure the preservation of the diverse religious heritage of the country.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Finally, it should be noted that The Places of Worship (Special Provisions) Act of 1991 is crucial for maintaining India's religious peace and secular framework. In especially in reaction to the Babri Masjid-Ram Janmabhoomi controversy, the Act was created to reduce communal tensions and disputes involving holy sites. The Act strives to preserve the holiness and integrity of these locations by maintaining the religious nature of houses of worship as they were in 1947.

The Act's aim of keeping religious sites as they are ensures that no alteration, conversion, or demolition could cause additional social conflict in the community. These locations are given legal protection, and it is acknowledged that dispute resolution procedures are necessary in the event that disagreements on their religious character should develop.

Although the Act has drawn criticism, notably because of its ability to uphold past injustices and hinder social advancement, it is essential to preserve the nation's unique religious legacy. The Act aims to promote religious harmony, religious tolerance, and India's unique cultural heritage by preserving the present religious identity of houses of worship.

It's essential to remember that the Act has restrictions because it only applies to religious buildings that existed before August 15, 1947, and it doesn't deal with disputes involving buildings that were built after that date.

The Places of Worship Act of 1991, in its whole, is a significant step towards preserving religious harmony and safeguarding India's secular values. The Act supports the preservation of India's rich religious history and emphasises the significance of communal peace and harmony in the nation by giving religious sites legal protection and freezing their religious identity.